

CHARACTERIZATION OF THE WATER SEDIMENTARY CONDITIONS OF ITAPUÃ BEACH, SALVADOR-BAHIA, DURING THE 2014 RAINY SEASON

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ABSTRACT

Bioclasts correspond to limestone skeletal remains of marine and/or freshwater organisms, which have a recognizable surface feature, and which therefore can be used in order to characterize the aquatic environment in terms of its hydrodynamics. Based on this aspect, this article aimed to characterize the hydro-sedimentary conditions of Itapuã beach, located in the city of Salvador - Bahia, using the biogenic/bioclast components of the sediment as descriptors. As for methodological aspects, 30 samples of surface sediments were collected, these points being distributed along the beaches of Farol de Itapuã, Rua K, Quiosque da Janaína and Sereia, 20 parallel to the beach face equidistant in 120m and 10 perpendicular with 50m of distance between the points, which were washed and dried in the laboratory and analyzed for their

bioclastic composition, taphonomy, distribution, granulometry and calcimetry. As for the results, it was possible to group the bioclasts into 16 biogenic categories, with the calcareous algae category (>55%) being the most abundant. A heterogeneous distribution was found, with a predominance of autochthonous grains, mottled in color, with abrasion, with rounding level 3 and relics, indicating that the surface sediments are being reworked in the analyzed area. Low carbonate values (> 48%) indicate a greater siliciclastic contribution and the predominance of the fine sand fraction indicates low hydrodynamics.

Keywords : Biogenic components. rainy season. Itapua beach.

INTRODUCTION

The sediment provides the researcher with multiple data, which may vary according to the level of knowledge applied to them, when studied from a physical, chemical and/or biological perspective, thus attributing particularities. Sediment can be divided into two major groups: (a) siliciclastic (or clastic) that originate from minerals and rock fragments and (b) bioclastic (biotic grains, biogenic components, biotrital grains), originating from fragments of animal and vegetable origin, presenting a recognizable surface feature (TINOCO, 1989).

Bioclastic grains can be found in various aquatic environments, such as open sea areas, estuarine areas, beaches and reefs. Among the organisms capable of supplying bioclasts to these types of environments, we can highlight calcareous algae, through the deposition of their cylindrical or globose body, diatoms with their frustules, foraminifera with their testa, echinoderms with their spines and exoskeleton, among others . (SANTOS and MORAES, 2011).

Biogenic material, when produced in situ, is called autochthonous grain, while those that tend to be transported to areas near or far from where they were produced are called allochthonous. Associated with taphonomic aspects, it is possible to study the participation rate of each group of organisms present in an area and describe their depositional history (GINSBURG, 1974).

According to Tinoco (1989), bioclastics are of great importance because they have a biological and stratigraphic meaning, which allows, for many times, to characterize the environment where they lived and in some cases can lead us to understand the age of the sedimentation. These sediments are widely used in agriculture as fertilizers, in animal nutrition, as implants in bone surgery, in water treatment and in the cosmetics industry, being a highly important resource for man (DIAS, 2000).

Based on these aspects, the general objective of this article is to characterize the hydro-sedimentary conditions of Itapuã beach, during the 2014 rainy season, using the sediment bioclasts as descriptors. Specific objectives include inventorying the main biogenic categories and knowing their distribution, evaluating the carbonate contributions in the total area and sub-beaches, determining the hydrodynamic energy and describing the pattern of transport and sedimentation of bioclastic grains.

Due to the importance of biogenic components, as indicators of the hydro-sedimentary conditions of aquatic environments, the present work is justified, since it contributes to a better description of such parameters by constituting a methodology that is easy to apply and requires low resources for its application, in addition to serving as a complementary source of information for the study of coastal environments.

STUDY AREA

The present study was carried out in the neighborhood of Itapuã, in the city of Salvador - BA, located on the Atlantic coast of the Bahian capital, with a variety of natural resources in the region, such as beaches, dunes and lakes. Itapuã beach is divided into four beaches: Farol de Itapuã, Rua K, Quiosque de Janaína and Sereia, with a total length of 1.5 km of beach (SILVA et al, 2009).

The beach was classified as intermediate, with the presence of sliding and plunging waves in certain stretches and with high hydrodynamic energy (SANTOS, 2010), consisting of coarse sand, a large amount of reefs and rocky bollards (NUNES, 1997). According to Santos, (2010) the advance of urbanization in the neighborhood led to the modification of native vegetation in the study area, from 1977 to 2010.

METHODOLOGY

The methodological procedures adopted were grouped into three stages, namely:

3.1 Field procedures

During the rainy season (May 2014) a sampling campaign was carried out in order to obtain 36 sedimentary samples, and due to the strong energy of the waves and the high pollution existing in some points, it was only possible to obtain 30 samples (Figure 1).

Figure 1 . Schematic map of the study area and distribution of sampling points

Source: Adapted from SILVA et al (2009)

The collection points were marked with the aid of a GPS and the sediment samples were collected manually, by inserting duly identified plastic containers with screw caps. Each sample, with approximately 300g of sediment, was stored for later analysis in the laboratory.

Laboratory procedures

a) Sediment analysis

The carbonate content analysis was performed according to Suguio (1973) and the samples were categorized into lithoclastic (carbonate content <30%), litho-bioclastic (30-50%), bio-lithoclastic (50-70%) and bioclastic (>70%) (DIAS, 1996).

The granulometric analysis was performed by dry sieving, adopting the fractions: gravel (4.000mm), coarse sand (2.000 - 1.000 mm), medium sand (0.500 mm), fine sand (0.250 - 0.125 mm and 0.062 mm) and mud (<0.062 mm).

b) Bioclast analysis

The samples were washed under running water in a sieve with a spacing of 0.062mm, dried in an oven at 60°C, and later, with the aid of a stereoscopic microscope, all grains of biogenic origin contained in one gram of sediment were sorted, identified and grouped into 15 categories according to Milliman (1974): coralline algae, Halimeda, diatom, foraminifera,

bryozoan, porifera, polychaete, barnacle, crab, gastropod, bivalve, scaphopod, echinoderm, aggregate and miscellaneous.

In addition, the taphonomic parameters were analyzed: (1) Coloring - the grains can be white, yellow, brown, black or mottled (LEÃO and MACHADO, 1989); (2) Degree of rounding - ranging from 0 (grain without rounding) to 4 (grain well rounded) according to the level of sphericity (PILKEY et al., 1967); (3) Wear - natural (unmodified), abrasion (with scratches and/or polished appearance), breakage (with loss of fragments and/or impact marks), dissolution (with peeling appearance and/or showing internal structures) or mixed (with two or more types of wear) (COTTEY and HALLOCK, 1988; MORAES and MACHADO, 2003) and (4) Sedimentation - current (clear and well-preserved components) or relics (dark and quite worn grains) (LEÃO and MACHADO, 1989; LIMA et al, 2008).

Based on the ecological characteristics of the organism that originated the biogenic structure, adopting the Kidwell, Fursich and Aigner (1986) classification, bioclasts were classified as: a) Allochthonous grains – originating from areas different from the one in which they are deposited; and b) Autochthonous grains – originating from the area where they are deposited.

c) Statistical analysis

For the analysis of the representativeness and distribution of the biogenic categories, the following were determined: absolute abundance, relative abundance and the Chi-Square Test (χ^2).

i) Absolute abundance: It is the number of times a certain variable (biogenic category) is repeated in a given sample (AB'SABER et al., 1997).

ii) Relative abundance: It is the ratio between the number of individuals in a category and the total number of individuals in all categories expressed as a percentage (AB'SABER et al., 1997). The relative abundance was calculated according to the following formula:

$$AR = (n \cdot 100) / N$$

Where: n is the number of individuals in a category and N is the total number of categories obtained in the sample. This criterion was used to determine the abundant biogenic categories at each collection point. For the interpretation of these results, the scale proposed by Dajoz (1983) was adopted:

Main – Values above 5%;

Accessory – Values between 4.9 and 1%;

Traces – Values less than 1%.

c) Chi-Square Test (χ^2): In this test, the total distribution of biogenic categories along Itapuã beach and its sub-beaches is evaluated, considering $p < 0.01$ as significant. Based on the results found, it was established whether or not there was homogeneity in the distribution of biogenic categories.

Chi-square was calculated according to the following formula:

$$\chi^2 = \sum \frac{(FO - FE)^2}{FE}$$

Where: $\sum$ is the sum of the observed frequency minus the expected frequency squared divided by the expected frequency, FO is the observed frequency of the categories and FE is the expected frequency for the categories to occur (CLEGG, 1995).

The degree of freedom adopted was based on the following formula: $\phi = NC - 1$

Where: NC is the number of biogenic categories studied.

With the chi-square analysis, with the degree of freedom equal to 14 and alpha (significance level) of 1%, the critical value of 29.1 was obtained, which was adopted for the evaluation of the degree of distribution of biogenic categories.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Representativeness of biogenic categories

In all, 9,000 bioclasts were analyzed throughout the studied area, distributed in 15 biogenic categories (Figure 2), with almost all autochthonous grains in the area, except for the presence of scaphopods (allochthonous grain).

The main bioclastic categories were calcareous algae (55.25%), foraminifera (19.21%), gastropod (6.16%) and crab (5.58%). The accessory ones comprised echinoderm (3.34%), bivalve (3.45%) and aggregate (4.91%). The least representative (trait category) included the genus alga *Halimeda* (0.81%), bryozoan (0.52%), polychaete (0.27%), porifera (0.17%), scaphopod (0.15%), diatom (0.05%), barnacle (0.03%), miscellaneous (0.03%) (Figure 2a).

Praia do Farol de Itapua

2700 bioclastic grains were analyzed (30% of the total sample in the study area), which were grouped into 15 categories (Figure 2b). The main one is represented by calcareous algae (53.25%), foraminifera (16.77%), crab (10.51%), aggregate (5.85%) and gastropod (5.18%), having as accessory categories, bivalve (3.92%) and echinoderm (2.81%) (Figure 2b).

Figure 2 - Relative abundance of biogenic categories found at Praia de Itapuã and its sub-beaches in May 2014 (rainy season)

K street beach

3000 grains were analyzed (33.33%), which were grouped into 13 categories (Figure 2c), the main ones being: calcareous algae (54.16%), foraminifera (20.96%), gastropod (6.5%) and echinoderm (5.13%). The accessory category consisted of crab (4.86%), bivalve (3.86%) and aggregate (2.3%). Barnacle and miscellaneous specimens were not recorded (Figure 2c).

Praia do Quiosque da Janaína

This region had a total of 900 grains (10%) analyzed, distributed into 11 categories (Figure 2d). Only calcareous algae (73.0%) and foraminifera (13.44%) were classified as major. In the accessory category there were gastropod (3.66%), aggregate (2.77%), crab (2.0%), bivalve (2.0%), echinoderm (1.88%). There was no record of diatom, porifera, barnacle and miscellaneous categories (Figure 2d).

Mermaid Beach

A total of 2400 grains (26.7%) were analyzed, which are grouped into 12 categories (Figure 2e), the main ones being: calcareous algae (52.2%), foraminifera (21.91%), echinoderm (8.12 %) and gastropod (7.41%). In the accessory category there were bivalve (2.95%), crab (2.29%) and aggregate (2.04%) (Figure 2e).

The high representation of algae is due to the fact that these organisms cover a large part of the outer shelf of the Northeast region. Its abundance is also related to physical-chemical factors (COUTINHO, 1981). The hydrodynamic energy of the location leads to their breaking and transport to the beach face, where rocky outcrops occur that force a decrease in hydrodynamics in the area close to the beach face, thus enabling their deposition (REBOUÇAS, 2006; SANTOS, 2008, 2010) .

According to Santos et al (2014), the abundance of foraminifera in the area is due to the fact that their testa tend to be transported from the open sea region towards the beach, where the presence of rocky outcrops creates a shadow area that lead to the reduction of hydrodynamics and allowing the deposition of testas.

The gastropod category is present on all beaches. Its broad representativeness may be related to its varied lifestyle habits (NASCIMENTO, 2008). In the area, their shells are retained among the rocks present, having the same great resistance, which made it possible to find them in perfect condition. This fact was also reported by Araújo (2012).

Barnacles have a tough exoskeleton that provides greater protection, and are only found at Farol de Itapuã. This low representativeness was also observed by Barros (1976) and Ferreira (2012) in the same locality. Its absence from the other beaches is certainly due to the smaller number of rocky outcrops.

Distribution of biogenic categories

The total value of the study area found in the Chi-square test ($\chi^2 = 41,410.92$), (with $p < 0.01$) shows that the biogenic categories are heterogeneously distributed.

For all four subbeaches, it was found that the distribution of bioclasts occurs heterogeneously, and on Farol de Itapuã beach, the value found in the Chi-square test was $2 = 2,088.68$, on Rua K $\chi^2 = 2,423.12$, at Quiosque de Janaína $\chi^2 = 608.59$ and at Sereia $\chi^2 = 1,853.20$, considering $p < 0.01$ for all.

The distribution is a reflection of the resistance of organisms in life and of bioclasts already deposited to the weathering forces existing there in the environment, such as the action

of waves, tides, their friction with the bottom sediments and their interaction with the physical-chemical parameters of the water (SANTOS, 2010).

Taphonomic signatures of biogenic components

a) Level of Rounding

The rounding level with the highest relative abundance in the four subbeaches of Itapuã was level 3 (Figure 3a), which obtained values greater than 50%. The second most frequent level, level 0 (> 11%), with the exception of Praia do Quiosque de Janaína, where level 2 was more expressive.

On all beaches, level 3 remains the most representative, and level 1 with the lowest percentage, and this data was also reported by Santos, (2010) when studying the bioclasts in the same area. Calcareous algae have the highest grain contribution rate at three levels: level 3 (70.71%), 4 (56.29%) and 1 (39.80), and foraminifera are the largest grain suppliers with the level 0 (88.09%) and 2 (24.39%), given the fact that these are indigenous organisms in the area.

b) coloring

The most representative color was mottled (44.01%), followed by brown (23.81%) and white (17.32%) (Figure 3b). Calcareous algae were the most abundant category for all patterns described, except for the white color, in which foraminifera obtained the highest percentage (24, 39%).

The coloration of the grains is related to the presence of iron mixed with water, leading the grains to colors such as yellow, brown and black, due to bacterial action or even due to pollution of organic origin (TINOCO, 1989), which was verified on the beach, in spots where the color of the water was black.

c) State of preservation

The abrasion state (66.23%) had a higher incidence on the beaches, followed by the natural state (14.02%), mixed (4.04%), broken (0.29%) and dissolved (0.02%) (Figure 3c). The major contributions were due to calcareous algae (66.25%), in relation to the state of abrasion.

Figure 3 - Relative abundance of taphonomic signatures of biogenic categories by subbeach of Itapuã neighborhood in May 2014 (rainy season)

The foraminifera provided the highest percentage of natural grains (50.29%), mixed (56.52%) and broken (50.52%). The dissolved pattern was divided with equal percentages for the calcareous algae (50.00%) and foraminifera categories.

The predominance of grains with abrasion indicates that the grains are transported by rolling, which allows the appearance of scratches on their surface (PILKEY et al., 1967). This data agrees with the grain rounding data, where there was a predominance of rounded grains (level 3).

The normal pattern is associated with new grains in the environment that have not been transported, while the mixed pattern corresponds to environments with oscillations in hydrodynamic energy (MORAES, 2006).

d) Sedimentation

Sedimentary analysis showed the highest amount of relic grains (62.42%), followed by current grains (37.58%). These results are repeated on all beaches (Figure 3d), with the calcareous algae category having the highest grain contribution to both types of sediments. This pattern is compatible with the registered color pattern, indicating that the bioclasts are mostly buried and exposed to the surface with the arrival of the rainy season (LIMA et al, 2008; SANTOS, 2010).

Granulometric features

The fine sand fraction (74.01%) is dominant on Itapuã beach, followed by medium sand fractions (21.96%), coarse sand (3.86%), mud (0.09%) and gravel fractions (0.07%). The granulometric features did not show many changes in the intensity of hydrodynamic energy in the subbeaches, all of which follow the same pattern (Figure 4). This analysis is a method that can help in the sedimentary characterization, as it is associated with the hydrodynamic processes of the locality (SUGUIO, 2003). areas.

This result is contrary to what was described by Nunes (1997), who characterized the area as being of coarse granulometry, which indicates that in more than 15 years, the hydrodynamic energy of the area has changed, tending to decrease.

Figure 4 - Relative abundance of granulometric features by subbeaches in the Itapuã neighborhood in May 2014 (rainy season).

Carbonate Content

The analysis of the carbonate content showed that the levels of CaCO₃ vary, with the litoclastic type being predominant in the subbeaches of Farol de Itapuã and in the subbeach of Rua K, the litho-bioclastic type in Quiosque de Janaína and Sereia. Thus, it appears that as we move from the subbeach of Farol de Itapuã, towards the subbeach of Sereia, there is a tendency to increase the levels of CaCO₃ in the subbeaches. The low values found in the Farol de Itapuã area are due to the presence of rocky outcrops that make it difficult for new bioclasts to enter the region, which does not occur in the Sereia subbeach.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

Based on the results obtained here, it can be concluded that the calcareous algae category is the most representative bioclast, while barnacle and miscellaneous have the lowest percentages, and all biogenic categories are heterogeneously distributed.

As for the carbonate content, there is a predominance of the lithoclastic type in the total area, and by subbeaches, there is a tendency for an increase in carbonate contributions from the region of Farol de Itapuã towards Sereia. The fine sand fraction is predominant, which indicates low hydrodynamics.

Grains with level 3 rounding and abrasion were dominant, indicating grain transport via rolling. The mottled and brown colors obtained the highest percentages, oscillating the same in some subbeaches, and for the sedimentation pattern there was a predominance of relic grains, which indicates that the sedimentation process in the area is old.

Based on these aspects, one can characterize Itapuã beach, according to the 2014 rainy season, as a beach with low hydrodynamic energy (predominance of fine sand) and low contribution of carbonate grains (dominance of siliciclastic grains).

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